

Нарзуллаев Ш.Ш., Бабажанов А.С., Давлатов С.С., Рахманов К.Э. <i>Обоснование хирургического вмешательства при узловых образованиях щитовидной железы с точки зрения клиники и морфологии</i>	202	Narzullaev Sh.Sh., Babajanov A.S., Davlatov S.S., Rakhmanov K.E. <i>Justification of surgical intervention for nodular thyroid lesions from a clinical and morphological perspective</i>
Неъматуллаева М.Л. <i>Последствия перенесенного COVID-19 и его влияние на качество жизни больных с патологией сердца</i>	208	Nematullayeva M.L. <i>The consequences of COVID-19 and its impact on the quality of life of patients with heart disease</i>
Нурова З.Х. <i>Кардиоэмболик инсультнинг ўтқир даврида беморларда даво усулларини танлаш ва клиник натижаларнинг ўзаро боғлиқлиги</i>	211	Nurova Z.Kh. <i>The choice of treatment methods for patients in the acute period of cardioembolic stroke and the relationship of clinical outcomes</i>
Паноев Х.Ш. <i>Значение морфо-функциональных показателей в прогнозе психомоторного развития детей</i>	215	Panoev Kh.Sh. <i>The importance of morphofunctional indicators in the prognosis of psychomotor development of children</i>
Pulatova P.H. <i>Yurakning koronar qon tomirlar kasalligi va buyrak funksiyasining buzilishi</i>	220	Pulatova P.Kh. <i>Coronary heart disease and kidney dysfunction</i>
Раджабова Г.Б. <i>Алгоритм прогноза осложнений при токсических алкогольных поражениях печени</i>	226	Radjabova G.B. <i>An algorithm for predicting complications in toxic alcoholic liver damage</i>
Расулова Н.А., Хабибова Н.Н. <i>Сравнительный анализ диагностической эффективности цитологических и иммуногистохимических методов в выявлении онкориска лейкоплакии у больных СД 2 типа</i>	233	Rasulova N.A., Khabibova N.N. <i>Comparative analysis of the diagnostic effectiveness of cytological and immunohistochemical methods in assessing oncological risk of leukoplakia in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus</i>
Rasulova N.R., Temirova N.R. <i>Tajribaviy kimyoterapiya ta'sirida ayrisimon bezdagi morfologik o'zgarishlar</i>	238	Rasulova N.R., Temirova N.R. <i>Morphological changes in the thymus under the influence of experimental chemotherapy</i>
Паноев Х.Ш. <i>Программа прогнозирования психомоторного развития детей дошкольного возраста</i>	243	Panoev Kh.Sh. <i>A program for predicting the psychomotor development of preschool children</i>
Рахимова Г.Ш., Тешаев Ш.Ж. <i>Экспериментда бош мия шикастланишидан кейинги еттинчи суткадаги уруғдонлардаги морфологик ўзгаришлар тавсифи</i>	247	Rakhimova G.Sh., Teshayev Sh.J. <i>Characteristics of morphological changes in the testes on the seventh day after traumatic brain injury in the experiment</i>
Рахматова С.Н., Джумаев Б.И. <i>Ўшларда ишемик инсультдан кейинги даврда беморларда хавф омиллари, этиопатогенетик турларининг учраш даражалари ва уларнинг клиник хусусиятлари</i>	251	Rakhmatova S.N., Dzhumaev B.I. <i>Risk factors in patients after ischemic stroke in young people, levels of occurrence of etiopathogenetic types and their clinical features</i>
Po'latova P.H. <i>Surunkali buyrak kasalligi va miokard infarkti - yuqori xavf kombinatsiyasi</i>	256	Pulatova P.Kh. <i>Chronic kidney disease and myocardial infarction are - a high risk combination</i>
Soliyev A.A. <i>Stomatologiya morfofunktsional tizimlar doirasida og'iz bo'shlig'i salomatligini ta'minlovchi fan sifatida</i>	261	Soliyev A.A. <i>Dentistry as a science ensuring oral health within the framework of morphofunctional systems</i>
Сабиров Б.К., Хабибова Н.Н. <i>Влияние хронической почечной недостаточности на состояние слизистой оболочки полости рта: диагностика и лечение воспалительных заболеваний</i>	264	Sabirov B.K., Khabibova N.N. <i>The influence of chronic renal failure on the condition of the oral mucosa: diagnosis and treatment of inflammatory diseases</i>

CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE AND MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION ARE - A HIGH RISK COMBINATION

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Resume. Recent studies have clearly demonstrated that impaired kidney function is strongly associated with an increased risk of cardiovascular complications. Large-scale clinical investigations have reported that 13.9–43.1% of patients with non-ST-segment elevation acute myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) exhibit renal dysfunction. According to the ACTION registry, chronic kidney disease (CKD) was identified in 30% of patients with ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) and in 43% of those without ST elevation. The TIMI and InTIME-II trials showed that 30-day mortality rates were 1.4, 2.1, and 3.9 times higher in patients with mild, moderate, and severe CKD respectively, compared to those with preserved renal function.

Key words: acute myocardial infarction, chronic kidney disease, glomerular filtration rate, invasive intervention, revascularization.

SURUNKALI BUYRAK KASALLIGI VA MIOKARD INFARKTI - YUQORI XAVF KOMBINATSIYASI

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Rezyume. So`nggi tadqiqotlar shuni ko`rsatmoqdaki, buyrak faoliyatining pasayishi yurak-qon tomir asoratlari xavfini sezilarli darajada oshiradi. Keng ko`lamli klinik kuzatuvlarga ko`ra, ST segmenti ko`tarilmagan o`tkir miokard infarkti (NSTEMI) bo`lgan bemorlarning 13,9–43,1 foizida buyrak faoliyati buzilishi aniqlangan. ACTION reyestri ma`lumotlariga ko`ra, ST segmenti ko`tarilgan infarkt (STEMI) holatlarida surunkali buyrak kasalligi (SBK) 30% holatda, ST ko`tarilmagan holatlarda esa 43% holatda aniqlangan. TIMI va InTIME-II tadqiqotlari shuni ko`rsatdiki, SBK darajasi yengil, o`rta va og`ir bo`lgan bemorlarda 30 kunlik o`lim darajasi buyrak faoliyati saqlanib qolgan bemorlarga nisbatan mos ravishda 1,4, 2,1 va 3,9 barobar yuqori bo`lgan.

Kalit so`zlar: o`tkir miokard infarkti, surunkali buyrak kasalligi, glomerulyar filtratsiya darajasi, invazivlik, revaskulyarizatsiya.

ХРОНИЧЕСКИЕ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЯ ПОЧЕК И ИНФАРКТ МИОКАРДА - СОЧЕТАНИЕ ВЫСОКОГО РИСКА

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Резюме. В последнее время убедительно доказано, что снижение функции почек тесно связано с увеличением риска развития сердечно-сосудистых осложнений. В ряде обширных клинических исследований сообщается, что у 13,9–43,1% пациентов с острым инфарктом миокарда (ОИМ) без подъема сегмента ST выявляется почечная дисфункция. По данным регистра ACTION, у больных с ОИМ и подъемом сегмента ST хроническая болезнь почек (ХБП) встречается в 30% случаев, а при отсутствии подъема ST — в 43%. Исследования TIMI и InTIME-II продемонстрировали рост 30-дневной смертности у пациентов с инфарктом и сопутствующей ХБП — в 1,4 раза при лёгкой, в 2,1 — при умеренной и в 3,9 раза — при тяжёлой степени, по сравнению с пациентами без нарушений функции почек.

Ключевые слова: острый инфаркт миокарда, хроническая болезнь почек, скорость клубочковой фильтрации, инвазивные вмешательства, реваскуляризация.

An important clinical challenge involves evaluating the efficacy and safety of revascularization strategies in the management of acute myocardial infarction (AMI), particularly among patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). In this population, limited application of invasive procedures often becomes a decisive factor when selecting initial treatment approaches. According to findings by G.W. Sadeghi et al., patients suffering from AMI and renal dysfunction who underwent coronary angioplasty exhibited a 5.8-fold increase

in 30-day mortality compared to those with preserved renal function. Additionally, the incidence of adverse events such as bleeding, restenosis, and reocclusion of the infarct-related artery was more than twice as high.

The GRACE study (2009) further highlighted that the utilization of reperfusion therapy declined in proportion to worsening renal function. Neither fibrinolytic therapy nor percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) showed a substantial reduction in in-hospital mortality among patients with renal insufficiency. Moreover, thrombolytic therapy was associated with a 35% increase in mortality risk. Nonetheless, in patients with moderate renal dysfunction who survived hospitalization, primary PCI—but not thrombolysis—was linked to a 59% reduction in 6-month mortality, although this benefit came at the cost of a heightened risk of bleeding.

Data from the EVENT research group (2009) indicate that optimal pharmacologic therapy remains the only consistently validated approach for improving prognosis in AMI patients with renal impairment. In contrast, observational research by D. Henry et al. demonstrated that early angiographic assessment and myocardial revascularization correlated with a reduction in mortality over a one-year period among patients with acute coronary syndrome (ACS) and advanced CKD, as compared to those managed medically.

Despite the increased risk of mortality and cardiovascular complications reported in retrospective studies involving CKD patients undergoing invasive AMI treatment, these analyses often inadequately account for the complex characteristics of the ACS population with concurrent renal dysfunction managed through early interventional strategies.

Materials and methods. A retrospective analysis was conducted based on the medical records of 181 patients with a confirmed diagnosis of acute myocardial infarction (AMI), who were admitted to the Bukhara Regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center between 2022 and 2025. Renal function was assessed in accordance with the recommendations provided by the Russian National Society of Cardiology (VNOK, 2013) and the Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO, 2013) guidelines. The glomerular filtration rate (GFR) was calculated using the CKD-EPI equation.

Data were analyzed both during the patients' hospital stay for AMI and six months following discharge. Cardiovascular complications and cases of cardiac-related mortality were systematically recorded. The median follow-up period was 18 months, with a range from 12 to 28 months.

For statistical analysis, quantitative differences between groups were assessed using the Mann–Whitney U test. Qualitative variables were evaluated using Pearson's χ^2 test with Bonferroni correction, Fisher's exact test, or the Monte Carlo method as appropriate. Survival outcomes were examined using Kaplan–Meier survival curves, with statistical significance determined by the log-rank test. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant for all analyses.

Results and Discussion.

Out of the 181 patients admitted with acute myocardial infarction (AMI), estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) at the time of hospitalization was calculated in 169 individuals, accounting for 93.3% of the cohort.

These 169 patients were divided into two groups based on renal function. Group 1 consisted of 114 individuals with preserved renal function (eGFR > 60 ml/min/1.73 m²), including 86 men (75%) and 28 women (25%), with a mean age of 61±11 years. Group 2 included 55 patients with impaired renal function (eGFR < 59 ml/min/1.73 m²), of whom 22 (40%) were men and 33 (60%) were women, with a significantly higher average age of 70.8±11 years. Statistically, reduced GFR was more prevalent in older individuals (p<0.001) and in women (p<0.001).

Compared to Group 1, patients in Group 2 had significantly higher frequencies of prior angina (63.6% vs. 35.9%, p=0.001), arterial hypertension (95.6% vs. 75.7%, p=0.004), and history of AMI (35.9% vs. 19.2%, p=0.021). Non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) was more frequent in Group 2 (75.6%) than in Group 1 (59%, p=0.041), whereas ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) was less prevalent in Group 2 (26.5%) compared to Group 1 (43%).

Coronary angiography was performed in 133 patients (80.2%). Among those, percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) with stent placement was executed in 89 patients (79.4%) from Group 1 and in 33 patients (59.4%) from Group 2 (p=0.01). Notably, significant stenosis (>50%) of the left coronary artery (LCA) trunk was identified more frequently in Group 2 (23.3%) than in Group 1 (6.9%, p=0.027).

During a median follow-up period of 18 months, the overall mortality rate was 10.3% (15 patients). The leading causes of death included chronic heart failure (58.3%), recurrent AMI (22.6%), progressive renal failure (15.4%), and cerebrovascular complications (6.9%). Group 2 experienced a markedly higher mortality rate during follow-up (79.5%) compared to Group 1 (22.3%, p=0.001), and overall survival was significantly lower (log-rank test = 0.002).

Analysis revealed that deceased patients were more likely to have undergone previous AMI or coronary artery bypass surgery (CABG) ($p=0.047$ and $p=0.021$, respectively). Univariate analysis using the Mann–Whitney U test indicated that older age significantly increased mortality risk (HR = 1.071; 95% CI: 1.1–1.13; $p = 0.006$). Elevated end-diastolic and end-systolic left ventricular volumes were also associated with a higher risk of death (HR = 1.016 and 1.023; $p = 0.018$ and 0.023, respectively). Importantly, stenosis of the LCA trunk $>50\%$ emerged as an independent predictor of long-term mortality in AMI patients with reduced GFR, increasing the risk of death nearly 19-fold (HR = 18.18; $p = 0.033$).

Despite a lower frequency of PCI among patients with decreased renal function, those in Group 2 who underwent stenting of the infarct-related artery demonstrated a significantly improved survival rate (log-rank test = 0.002).

These findings highlight a greater burden of comorbidity and worse outcomes in AMI patients with advanced renal impairment. The presence of LCA trunk stenosis $>50\%$ notably increased the likelihood of fatal events. Although high-grade CKD often limits the application of PCI due to concerns over contrast-induced nephropathy, our results support the notion that early revascularization may enhance survival even in patients with severely reduced renal function.

Conclusion. Thus, we can draw the following conclusions:

1. Patients with acute myocardial infarction (AMI) and reduced glomerular filtration rate (GFR) exhibit a higher prevalence of comorbid conditions compared to those with preserved renal function, contributing to a more complex clinical course and worse prognosis.

2. Significant stenosis of the left coronary artery (LCA) trunk exceeding 50% was identified as an independent and powerful predictor of long-term mortality in AMI patients with impaired renal function.

3. Implementation of early percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) in AMI patients with low GFR was associated with improved survival outcomes, in contrast to conservative treatment approaches, despite the challenges posed by chronic kidney disease (CKD) during invasive management.

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